

Collection of Chigatai Coins in Samarkand State Museum-Reserve

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Abstract: This article discusses the collection of coins belonging to the Chigatai state, stored in the funds of the Samarkand State Museum-Reserve, its rarity, value, the structure of coins and money, their signs, stamps, weights, the importance of monetary reforms.

Keywords: Ulus, monetary reform, dirham, dinar, "kepaki", stamp, anonymous.

INTRODUCTION

The monetary issues of the Chigatai state are considered to be among the most controversial issues, causing many disputes.

The insufficient study of written sources relating to the Chigatai ulus of the 13th-14th centuries further increases the importance of numismatic sources from this period as the main source of information. In addition, compared to the number of coins of the Golden Horde or the Hulagu state, the fact that Chigatai coins of this period have been preserved attracts the attention of many scholars more.

A number of studies of coins of the Chigatai period conducted by scientists have served to study many collections. In the past period, coins minted and put into circulation by the rulers of this state in various regions included in the territory of the Chigatai state have been found, studied, analyzed and compared with coins found in other regions.

Of great importance among such collections is the collection of 236 coins belonging to the rulers of the Chigatai state which was found in June 2022 in the territory of Bukhara and entered as a unique collection in the collection of the Samarkand State Museum-Reserve. This coin collection consists of 80 dinars and 156 dirhams minted in the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand, Termez and Utrar. These coins, minted from silver, have inscriptions in the Arabic alphabet on both sides and remnants of stamps.

The coins of Chigatai period preserved in the funds of Samarkand State Museum-Reserve were found only in Samarkand region, while the coins of this period found in Bukhara region were not in the museum funds until now. This collection of coins is an important numismatic source not only for Samarkand museums, but also for studying the history of the Chigatai period in the field of history.

The collection of coins found in Bukhara was minted by Kebek Khan, Tarmashirin, Bayonkuli Khan and other rulers and was in circulation from the first quarter of the 14th century until the emergence of the Amir Temur state. The appearance, weight standards, symbols on the coins and inscriptions of these coins have similarities and differences with the coins which were previously in museum collections.

If we interpret the coins of the Chigatai period by the same weight and denomination, only one full-weight Otor dirham is known. But this coin is one of the rarest coins. Coins found in Samarkand and Bukhara regions and kept in the museum collection do not belong to the Otrar coins, it is scientifically proved that their weight and value standards are at different levels. The coins found in Bukhara region also have different weight and denomination.

The collection of information about the coins of the Middle Ages of Central Asia began only in the middle of the 19th century. In the second half of the 20th century, M. Masson and E. Davidovich [1] made the first attempts to study and analyze data related to the circulation of known coins and money. As a result of their research only one collection of coins and money of the Talas valley was limited to the XIV century by M. Masson, and the issues of coinage and money circulation in the last quarter of the XIII century in the central regions of the Chigatai state were considered by E. Davidovich [10; pp. 45-67].

By the end of the 1960s, scientists found unique finds of the XIII-XIV centuries, and the geography of finds related to the circulation of coins and money even more expanded. In addition to Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Afghanistan, the regions of Xinjiang (PRC) and Khorasan (Iran) have attracted the attention of scholars.

The study of images of coins of Chigatai period, inscriptions on coins, stamps, their chronological analysis, topographical study of minting places also allows making important conclusions about when, where, what ruler coins were minted and put into circulation, as well as in solving problems about borders of the country during this ruler.

MAIN PART

It is known that as a result of the Mongol invasion the agricultural and handicraft areas of Maverannahr and Khorezm were destroyed. The densely populated cities, especially Bukhara, Samarkand, Urgench, Marw, Banokat, Hojent, and others, were turned into ruins. The main dam of the Merv oasis irrigation network, the famous Sultanband, was demolished. The residents of Samarkand were forced to leave their hometown. And the inhabitants of the Marv oasis left their land, which was drying up from dehydration, and went to other places and settled down. Urgench was flooded and completely destroyed. Many towns were set on fire. The wintering population of Khorezm and Maverannahr was sharply reduced. As a result, agriculture was in crisis. Economic life collapsed.

After the death of the great ruler of the Mongol kingdom Genghis Khan, his sons-Juchi, Chigatai, Oktai, and Tulukhan ruled the territories of his state. The territories of Eastern Turkestan, Semirech and Maverannahr were mainly given to Chigatai and his successors, and this territory went down in history under the name of Chigatai ulus. After the formation of the Chigatai ulus and as a result of reforms in the social, economic, and political spheres carried out by the rulers of the ulus, urban life, especially crafts and trade relations gradually, though steadily, began to revive in Maverannahr. In the same process, important measures arise that would stimulate the revival of the economic and social life of the country.

The level of economic and political sustainability of every state that has existed in history is directly related to the reforms in various spheres carried out by the rulers of the state. Among them, the reforms carried out in the monetary sphere are of particular importance. As a result of the monetary reform of the Chigatai rulers, the state developed domestic trade, which, in turn, led to the expansion of foreign trade, as well as the development of commodity-money relations in the country. Coins were minted and issued in many cities of the Chigatai ulus, including Bukhara, Tashkent, Ozer, Uzgan, Taraz, Kashgar, and Osh.

Reforms of the Mongolian state in social, economic, and political spheres, although they could not change the existing political order, influenced the life of different social strata in the country in different ways. The end of the 13th century was the heyday of the Chigatai state. At that time, the territory of the ulus stretched from the Amu Darya in the south of the Aral Sea to the Altai Mountains on the present border of Mongolia and China. This roughly corresponds to the territory of the Karakhanid Khanate. In the 1340s the state was divided into Mongolia and Maverannahr.

In 1271 a monetary reform was carried out by the rulers of Chigatai, as well as by the viceroy Masudbek. As a result of the Chigatai monetary reform coins of pure silver weighing 2 grams were minted and put into circulation.

Prior to the reform, mints associated with money circulation regularly minted silver coins in a number of cities in Central Asia - in cities such as Taraz, Otrar. These coins, owned by Mongol rulers, were silver dirhams minted at the mints of the city of Otrar, with the stamp of Otrar on the coins.

Masudbek's reform initially influenced the Central Asian mints. Silver dirhams were first regularly minted in this area in 1271-1272. E. Davidovich attributes the beginning of the Masudbek reform exactly to the time when several mints in Central Asia began to put into regular circulation silver coins of the same pattern and weight [2; pp 13-15].

As for Masudbek's reform, the issue that was complex and caused much debate among scholars was the question of the weight standards for minting silver dirhams. E. A. Davidovich in his work notes that the weight norm did not change during the issue of post-reform coins and that the specified weight was about 2.1 g, and remedium-about 0.1 g in each direction of the specified weight.

During the study of the dirhams minted in the first five years after the reform, three weight norms were established:

- 1) weight norm 1.38 ± 0.02 g (diameter 20.5 ± 0.3 mm);
- 2) weight norm 1.04 g 15;
- 3) weight norm 0.7 g; diameter 16.5-17.5 mm. [9; pp 205-206]

The activities of Kebek Khan and his reform on economic, social, political development of the state among the Mongolian rulers, on the establishment of diplomatic relations for state security, also have a place in the study of the history of the Chigatai ulus. According to this reform carried out in Maverannahr in 1321, coins could only be minted in the Chigatai ulus in the name of the great khan. The monetary reform carried out by Kebekhan led to the minting in the country of a large silver coin weighing 8 grams, equal in weight and value, - "Dinar", and a small silver coin weighing 1 gram - "dirham". On these coins were engraved the Turkish words "May he be blessed". One important aspect of the Kebek Khan reform was that it put an end to arbitrariness in matters relating to the minting, issuing of coin-coins into circulation.

These silver coins, known as "kepaks" in the early years of the Kebek-khan reforms, were minted and issued at the mints in Samarkand and Bukhara. Reformation was continued under Tarmashirin, who ruled from 1326 to 1334. Therefore, historian P. Petrov believes that it is more correct to call this reform by the name of two khans - kebek-tarmashirin. [6; pp 109-111]

According to the monetary reform carried out by the Tarmashirin, a silver dirham weighing 1.34 grams was minted, which was 1/6 of the Dinar. The Tarmashirin introduced the minting and use in circulation of pure silver coins, corresponding to the same weight standards. As a result, the number of mints in the country increased. To such mints as Samarkand, Bukhara, Termez were added mints in New Taraz, Otrar, Badakhshan.

Coins minted during his time bear the names of Tarmashirin and his son Sanjar. Silver coins minted during the Tarmashirin period have been found and researched in Samarkand, Bukhara, Eastern Turkestan and other areas of Central Asia.

Another aspect of importance in the study of coins of the Chigatai period is the appearance of coins and the presence of symbols, stamps and various inscriptions on them. The appearance of the dinars of the Chigatai era was varied. Their common distinctive feature is the Chigatai sign in the form of the letter "F" on a horizontal line, as well as the dividing sign in the form of a circle with two petals on the edges, wrapped with a horizontal line. The collection of Alamlyk, Termez coins can be attributed to coins with such a stamp in the shape of the letter "F". The coins had another stamp that looked as if the letter "S" was engraved with a dash at the waist. Coins with this stamp were minted in Bukhara, Samarkand, Termez, Shash, Taraz and other cities [2; pp 62-74.]

Coins with chigatai minting in both forms are found both on coins found in the Bukhara area and on coins of Samarkand. From this we can see that the coins are minted, put into circulation, their structure, the images on the coins have a similarity with the surrounding areas, if we consider them as examples of cities. The coins of Andijan, Samarkand, Khojent have mostly words written on them. This is more common in copper-coated dirhams [2; pp. 109-111.]

Coins anonymous were also presented in the form of various stamps. Coins minted in anonymous form do not mention the name of the ruler, inscriptions reflecting the belonging of the state to its place as an independent state are one of the main symbols of an independent state, the names of toponymic territories are marked, and coins of this type were minted in the central cities of the Chigataid state.

Unlike anonymous coins, the Chigatai state also had coins in circulation on which the name of the same ruler was inscribed. Such coins were minted and put into circulation by such rulers of this state as Kebek-Khan, Tarmashirin, Sanjar, Bayonkulikhan, among the powerful and diplomatic rulers.

During this period there was also the ruler's own personal seal of the state, and some of the coins from this period also had images on stamps. Now, if we compare in appearance the coins in circulation during the Chigatai period on the example of cities, the distinguishing feature of Samarqand coins from those of other cities is that the year of coinage is clearly indicated on these coins(681-693). On the obverse of their common sign in two rows in lower-case letters is written the name of the city of Samarkand, and on the reverse side in four rows is written the Sunni creed [2; pp. 36-45.]

The silver coins of Khojent, Andijan, Shash, Taraz, Otror are very similar in appearance. Scales, Shashi coins have the same two-line note, located in a square, and on the sides-small notes, sometimes readable, sometimes unreadable. On the reverse side is a stamp, under the stamp is the name of the mint. The content of pure silver in the coins of the Chigatai state was 74-81%.

CONCLUSION

Numismatic sources relating to the Chigatai era have a large territory in territorial terms. The study of the rulers who played a key role in maintaining a certain level of development of economic life in the Chigatai state, the regulation of fees, taxes, monetary circulation and monetary reforms carried out by them gives important conclusions for historical science.

Such cities as Samarkand, Bukhara, Shosh, Otror, which in different periods of history, during the rule of different states had the status of the main central cities, due to their position played their role in the implementation of the monetary reform, in particular, in the establishment of the mints. In particular, in the Chigatai state there were main mints in these cities. However, based on the fact that coins in the minted cities, although in large quantities, but relatively little studied, we can conclude that the coins of the Chigatai state found in Bukhara and stored today in Samarkand State Museum-Reserve are important. Another important aspect is that the collection of coins found in the Bukhara area is still recognized as very rare in the museum collections, and this, in turn, determines the need for extensive historical and scientific research, which should be conducted with regard to the medieval Chigatai numismatics. Thanks to the images, remnants of stamps, various inscriptions reflected on the coins, we not only get information about the rulers of the Chigatai state, the territory of the state, governance structures, features of the ruler of the state, but also once again we are convinced of the high importance of numismatic sources as the main source when studying the history of states, coverage of historical facts about it.

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